

Point of Interest and Stop Type Prediction with Artificial Neural Network for Transportation Data

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Abstract- This paper describes the design of a system to detect stop type in traffic data and detect the point of interest that causes two types of stopping, such as traffic jam and waiting time for sufficient numbers (of passengers) based on hours, days and location in the Bandung City, Indonesia. The method used in this paper uses neural networks after labeling the test data has been correlated.(result tambahin dikit)

Index Terms- Machine Learning, Big Data, Transportation Data.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the city development in big cities has increased with economic development. The impact of land use effects on people's travel through the transportation system. In response, developing transportation also plays a high role on the development and utilization of city [1][2]. The high level of infrastructure development in big cities is also accompanied by increasing traffic congestion. Sometimes the congestion or traffic jam that occurs is not merely due to traffic lights or accidents only, there can also be obstacles in the form of locations or places that are the source of congestion in the area. In the case studies in Indonesia, there are still public transports that do not have certain stop points, causing random stops to occur, and detecting traffic jam becomes more difficult. Nowadays, public transportation data is the right target for developers to analyze their behavior and point of deviation. But sometimes the problem faced is on the data stop, when the transportation data shows the speed at point 0 km/s, there is no explanation whether the data stops for some reason, also there are many possibilities that cause the data to stop at a certain point. The purpose of this paper is to detect the point of interest from existing transportation data, differentiate the types of stops based on the hours, days and buildings around the nodes.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

A. A Set of rules that used for labeling types of stops data

Jelasin ttg angkot nya juga

On this paper, we use the "Angkot" data in Bandung city, their stop points are too random caused the lower service quality drives more passengers to find another transportation mode [3]. Public transportations becoming less attractive and more expensive; Private cars or online sharing transportation services are becoming more attractive. The maximum number of fleets permitted by the government is more than 5500, the actual number of Angkot that

are still operating at this time has been reduced to 30%, or around 1,600 fleets. This was mainly due to the increase in private vehicle ownership in Bandung. In 2016, there were more than 1.7 million private vehicles [4]. There are 683 private vehicles for every 1000 population and 0,64 Angkot per 1000 population. Public transport availability in Kota Bandung is still below developing countries standard for bus transportation planning (1.5 per 1000 population) and Europe standard (1 bus per 1000 population) [5].

Angkot itself does not have a static stop point, but they have a certain point where they usually waiting for passengers. For example, to calculate its waiting time, let's take a several assumptions based on traffic data, the waiting time between Angkot in a certain place is 0,53 to 8,5 minutes with average waiting time is 2 minutes. Compare to Singapore MRT's waiting time (2-3 minutes during peak hours and 5-7 minutes during off peak times). However, Angkot's waiting time is still in reasonable range [6].

The set of rules were made from an assumption, such as:

Table 1 : Rules for each stops type

Type of stops	Rules
Traffic jam /Congestion	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• There are other intersections within a radius of +-500 meters ahead.• There is a traffic light within +-100 meters ahead.• School / mall / Traditional market / public service office within a radius of +- 500 meters ahead.
Drop passengers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Stop in +- 2 minutes
Waiting for passengers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Schools / hospitals / traditional markets / malls / public service offices +- 50 meters forward and +- 50 backward• Stop between 0.53 minutes to 8.5 minutes

Example of plotting data based on the rules above, the stop data plotted for 7 minutes within 12 meters from the school:

Fig.1 Illustration for plotting data

So that, the data clearly marked as “Waiting for passengers” type.

The rules that we mentioned above are using several building points data, such as school, hospital, mall, traditional market, traffic light, intersections, and public services. After being able to distinguish the types of stops, we can also determine the points of interest, in this paper we use the data that only contains "traffic jam" or "waiting for passengers" data for predicting their point of interest, we don't need to detect the point of interest where the transportation drop the passengers, because dropping the passengers can be anywhere without any certain pattern. The set of rules for predicting point of interest such as:

Table 2 : Rules for each buildings type

Type of Buildings	Rules
Campus	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weekday (Mon- Fri) 8.30AM-10.30AM 12.30PM-1.30PM 4PM-5PM
School	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weekday (Mon-Fri) 6.30AM-7AM 3PM – 4PM
Hospital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Everyday (Mon-Sun) 12PM-1PM 6PM-7PM
Mall	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weekday (Mon-Fri) 5PM–8PM Weekend (Sat-Sun) 12PM-2PM 4PM-7PM 9PM-10PM
Traditional Market	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Everyday (Mon-Sun) 3AM-5AM 7AM-9AM 12PM-1.30PM 5.30PM-7PM
Public Service Office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weekday (Mon-Fri) 7.30AM-10.30AM

This is an example of data before processing and after processing:

_id	Time	id	latitude	longitude
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:06:27.587	9	-6.89017	107.5843
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:07:27.340	9	-6.90739	107.6069
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:07:49.263	9	-6.87463	107.5895
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:08:27.827	9	-6.8908	107.5996
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:09:29.091	9	-6.888	107.5719
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:09:30.412	9	-6.88293	107.5691
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:10:34.671	9	-6.89533	107.5602

Fig.2 Illustration for data table before pre-processing

_id	Time	id	latitude	longitude	stop_type
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:06:27.587	9	-6.89017	107.5843	2
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:07:27.340	9	-6.90739	107.6069	2
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:07:49.263	9	-6.87463	107.5895	2
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:08:27.827	9	-6.8908	107.5996	2
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:09:29.091	9	-6.888	107.5719	2
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:09:30.412	9	-6.88293	107.5691	2
5a778609;	2018-02-04/17:10:34.671	9	-6.89533	107.5602	2

Fig.3 Illustration for data table after pre-processing

the process of labeling data is done manually without machine learning first, each stop type value has a number that represents the stop type in numerical data:

Table 3 : Value for stop type in numerical

Type of stops	Value
Traffic jam /Congestion	0
Drop passengers	1
Waiting for passengers	2

After labeling the stop types, we can continue the process to determine the type of point of interest based on the type of stop obtained from preprocessing. Only "traffic jam" dan "waiting for passengers" data type are involved in determining the point of interest.

Time	id	latitude	longitude	stop_type	point_of_i
2018-02-04/17:06:27.587	9	-6.89017	107.5843	2	1
2018-02-04/17:07:27.340	9	-6.90739	107.6069	2	1
2018-02-04/17:07:49.263	9	-6.87463	107.5895	2	1
2018-02-04/17:08:27.827	9	-6.8908	107.5996	2	1
2018-02-04/17:09:29.091	9	-6.888	107.5719	2	1
2018-02-04/17:09:30.412	9	-6.88293	107.5691	2	1
2018-02-04/17:10:34.671	9	-6.89533	107.5602	2	1

Fig.4 Illustration for data table after pre-processing for point interest

We also using the numerical data for labeling point of interest data

Table 4 : Value for point of interest type in numerical

Point of interest	Value
Campus	0
Mall	1
School	2
Hospital	3
Traditional Market	4
Public Service Office	5

B. Machine Learning.

Over the past two decades Machine Learning has become one of the main topic in information technology [7]. On this paper we will use MLP (Multilayer perceptron) or known as backpropagation. As already mentioned in the history of neural networks, the perceptron was described by Frank Rosenblatt in 1958 [8]. Initially, Rosenblatt discussed weighted a non-linear

activation function as components of the perceptron. Backpropagation itself is a supervised machine learning type, part of artificial neural network with multi-layered perceptron and gradient descent procedure (including all strengths and weakness of the gradient descent) with the error function $Err(W)$ receiving all weights as arguments [9].

This research using MLP for automation labeling stop types for transportation data that has not been labeled. The main reason for using machine learning is because the models are exposed to new data. They learn from previous computations to produce reliable, repeatable decisions and results. Resurging interest in machine learning is due to the same factors that have made data mining and Bayesian analysis more popular than ever. Things like growing volumes and varieties of available data, computational processing that is cheaper and more powerful, and affordable data storage.

The MLP model that we propose on this paper for predicting stop type are using this following feature:

Input Layer $\in \mathbb{R}^4$ Hidden Layer $\in \mathbb{R}^4$ Output Layer $\in \mathbb{R}^3$

Fig.5 Illustration for Neural network architecture for predict stop types.

Based on Fig.5, input layers containing 4 attributes in data such as latitude, longitude, time, day, while the output layer is the type of stop that is obtained in the pre-processing process, such as traffic jam, drop passengers and waiting passengers. Hidden layer is determined according to previous research by Nayer Wanas et al ,they mentioned on their research that the optimal number of hidden layers is $\log(T)$ where T is the number of sample data [10], so that $\log(5000) = 3.6 = 4$, we assume the data for beginning step will be 5000 data.

Table 5 : Layer information for fig. 5

Layer type	value
Input (4)	Latitude, Longitude, Time, Day
Hidden (4)	$\log(5000)$
Output (3)	Traffic jam, Drop passengers, Waiting Passengers

After predicting the data stops type, we can also implement the same way with point of interest data prediction, giving this neural network architecture as:

Input Layer $\in \mathbb{R}^5$ Hidden Layer $\in \mathbb{R}^6$ Output Layer $\in \mathbb{R}^6$

Fig.6 Illustration for Neural network models for predict stop types.

Based on what we see in Fig.6, the input layer consists of 5 layers, there are latitude, longitude, time, day, and stop type attributes. The output layer past 6 represents the points of interest that already defined in Table 4, while 1000 datasets are used for data training. Hidden layer obtained from $\log(1000) = 3$.

III. RESULT

The beginning process is to determine the most stop point is to map data by mapping the congestion histogram that is spread in Bandung city on all existing data. (legend tambahin)

Fig.7 Bar chart illustrates the level of congestion in various districts on Bandung

In Fig 7 we can see that the districts with the most stop points are *Cicendo* and *Sukajadi*, then we map the congestion in the form of a heatmap to see detailed location of the most stop points, to filter out more detailed areas on the map. First by first we must filter out “Drop passengers” data before we start to plot.

Fig.8 Heatmap for Angkot num.7

Fig.10 Heatmap and radius point of interest candidate

Fig.9 Heatmap for Angkot num.8

The fig.8 and fig 9 using 8AM - 10AM on Monday for example data plotting. Different id also different routes and different stop points, as we can see on fig 8 and 9 show us a different visualization heatmap. But they also have the resemblance when we take a look at *Cicendo* and *Sukajadi* district, they both also have a high stop point. So we can immediately select the part that stops the most to be eliminated such as the orange and yellow parts, then followed by parts that have a lower value like green and blue.

In fig.10 using 2AM- 6AM, and 5PM-7PM on Monday, we have a detailed picture of stops point when it's zoomed in, there are the most valuable area in *sederhana* streets. There is also a traditional market point exist, and it will be a point of interest candidate if we check the rules on Table. 2 for data which belongs to radius. As in fig.11 all data in radius are labelled with "Traditional Market" for it's point of interest.

devicetime	id	latitude	longitude	Stop type	Point_of_interest
2018-02-04T17:21:37.000Z	8	-6.88997	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T17:21:37.000Z	8	-6.88997	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T17:21:37.000Z	8	-6.88997	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T17:21:37.000Z	8	-6.88997	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T18:48:25.000Z	8	-6.88999	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T18:48:25.000Z	8	-6.88999	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T18:48:25.000Z	8	-6.88999	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T18:48:25.000Z	8	-6.88999	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T18:48:25.000Z	8	-6.88999	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T18:48:25.000Z	8	-6.88999	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T18:48:25.000Z	8	-6.88999	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market
2018-02-04T18:48:25.000Z	8	-6.88999	107.5997	2	Traditional_Market

Fig.11 Bar chart illustrates the level of congestion in various districts on Bandung

We repeat this process based on Table.2 Rules until all data labelled. Unfortunately for now there are only about 7000 data that already exist for label in point of interest and stop type.

A 5000 data samples are used for training ,2000 others are for testing data. We have train our ANN models with current dataset ,here's the result :

Fig.12 Training Result

The models are not enough producing high accuracy, this is caused of a limited dataset, the accuracy stats only reach 35% accuracy. We don't continue to train data for predict point of interest until the dataset are fully labeled.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper propose a method of prediction system for detecting different points of interest and types of stops. As for what we did, we have already collected 7000 data to be labeled, looking at the prediction results in Fig.12, this shows us a dataset is a mandatory things to be build first before do the train, the number of dataset available that are ready train is very small so that it shows poor accuracy.

There is still much that can be developed, moreover the design will not stop here, in the future we will add more types of point of

interest, and reverse detection as can detect how severe the level of congestion when installed one point of interest in the area.

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